

USE OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHER'S PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY

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Annotation.

This article provides information on the importance of modern information and communication technologies in improving pedagogical skills, using the capabilities of computers in the educational process, controlling students' knowledge by a teacher based on computer technology, using modern information technologies in the teacher's professional development.

Key phrases.

modern information and communication technologies (ICT), educational process, computer technologies, control of students' knowledge with the help of computer technologies, teacher's competence in using modern ICT;

Importance of modern information and communication technologies in improving pedagogical skills - Systematic integration of educational process with information and communication technologies is one of the important directions of educational system reform. In this case, the organization of the educational process and the fundamental renewal of its content, the organization of the pedagogical activity of the teacher and the educational process of the student in the atmosphere of information and communication technologies appear as a strategic issue.

At the developing stage of scientific and technical development, the sharp increase in information and the limitation of time to use it in the teaching process require the introduction of new technologies into the educational system. One of the directions of improving the content of education is to create the necessary conditions for the formation and development of independent education opportunities for students, information sources of education. The basis of educational processes is a high-quality and high-tech environment. Although its creation and development are considered technically complex, such an environment serves to improve the educational system and to introduce information technologies in education in the truest sense.

Modern information technologies have great opportunities for students in processes such as information delivery, storage, and search. Currently, many information and educational resources have been created in electronic form in educational institutions.

The direction of the development of informatization of educational processes is directly related to the creation of information-educational environments through the integration of various educational information resources. In the creation of such an environment, the first priority is the society of informatization in educational institutions, that is, all educational, executive and economic services, library and management departments into a single network, creating opportunities for them to access the Internet system, monitoring the educational process in the educational institution, organizing electronic exchange of documents, creating special educational and methodological complexes based on information technologies, independent educational activities of students it will be necessary to perform tasks such as organization. Currently, in the performance of such tasks, it is possible to organize the use of information and educational resources by creating portal technologies. The use of information and telecommunication technologies in the educational process is an important direction for the development of a unified information-educational environment of an educational institution. Systematization of information facilitates the use of information and educational resources. The creation of information and educational portals helps to organize and systematize information logically.

A systematic approach to the creation and development of information-educational portals is necessary. Because in creating an educational environment based on computer technologies, it is important to have a good level of analytical preparation, to ensure the appropriateness of the content, and to ensure the systematization of information.

A portal is a network telecommunication node that combines various information resources to deliver information to the user through simple navigation and a wide range of convenient interfaces. Based on this, the following requirements can be placed on the portals:

- serving a large number of users;
- breadth of information;
- use of main network formats;
- introduction of an easy and effective search system;
- integration of information resources;
- ensure information security;

- classification of information;
- knowledge management-analysis;

The index of portals is determined by the volume of information embodied in it, that is, the volume of information resources.

The goal of any portal is to provide the user with the necessary information in a short time and without unnecessary transitions between different interfaces. The user interface of the portal should visually display the content of the resources placed in it, provide a logical and quick transition from one section to other pages. The provided information and educational resources will include tasks for independent learning, tests to check acquired awareness, tasks aimed at developing creative thinking, and exercises aimed at strengthening knowledge.

When choosing multimedia materials for the portal, it is necessary to pay attention to their information content, structural composition, coherence and forms of information presentation. Multimedia materials should serve for easy assimilation of information: they should reveal their content, that is, they should be used as an independent source of information.

Technologically, information and education portals have the following requirements:

- ✓ execution of applications;
- ✓ ensuring cooperative activities;
- ✓ management of available resources;
- ✓ user management control;
- ✓ ensuring communication;
- ✓ provide search;
- ✓ protect all resources from unauthorized access, ensure information security;

The information-educational portal for fields of knowledge or subjects is not limited only to educational institutions. It is important that traditional and electronic educational materials complement each other as a component of a unified educational environment. Using the possibilities of new information technologies serves to eliminate difficulties in solving some pedagogical problems.

Information-educational portals can be considered as providing effective integration of science-education-production, creating conditions for organizing its development, effective use of scientific-pedagogical potential. It is also useful for customers who need graduates of educational institutions. The portal serves as a source of information on graduates. In addition, it establishes a new form of interaction with the providers of educational services and its consumers.

To create and develop such a portal, first of all, it is necessary to improve the computerization of educational institutions, further develop telecommunication networks, systematize information and place them on the portal. In addition, it is important to develop the skills of pedagogical personnel in the use of new information technologies in the educational system, and to develop their regular improvement. An important condition for the development of a unified information-educational environment is the development of the educational and methodological support of the portal, the improvement of the creation of electronic educational publications. In order to ensure the effective development of the information process, it is necessary to pay attention to the perfect formation of the information infrastructure.

Use of computer capabilities in the educational process - There are many advantages of using Web sites in educational processes. Therefore, the creation and updating of such sites is of great importance in the activity of the educational institution. Therefore, the creation of dedicated sites for educational institutions is one of the primary tasks facing each educational institution. When studying the creation of such sites, it is necessary to take into account the factors related to the Internet system. The following can be mentioned as such factors:

- ✓ the breadth of Internet service opportunities around the world;
- ✓ ease of use of the website service;
- ✓ convenience in distributing Web technologies;
- ✓ requirements for information on a real-time scale;
- ✓ institutions and private individuals seek to post information about themselves on the Internet;
- ✓ collection of intended information on a global scale in the network database.

The following types of Web sites are available on the Internet today:

❖ Advertising site - serves to advertise a specific product and service or brand in the Internet information situation, like chosen advertising. It is notable by the use of a large number of graphic elements and multimedia tools (Flash) on the pages.

❖ Information site - serves to provide visitors with complete information about products and services to remove the "information barrier" when making a decision to create a virtual connection of customers. The pages are notable by their appearance, because all the elements on this website serve to quickly and conveniently search and find information.

❖ Business site - serves to organize separate external business processes of the company products in the warehouse of suppliers and dealers; orders for obtaining products or services, training of employees and dealers; processes for conducting interviews are correct about). It is distinguished by the presence of software modules (internet application) for organizing business processes.

❖ The corporate portal includes the services of the company's internal and external business processes. In addition, the corporate portal includes information exchange between different departments of the company, accounting applications, warehouse, personnel department, statistical and analytical information, educational information; automated tools for working with suppliers, dealers, consumers, etc. enters. An internet application for organizing business processes is distinguished by the presence of interfaces for accessing practical programs used in the company (accounting, warehouse, planners, etc.).

❖ Sites dedicated to education and training. Such sites are mainly created in order to introduce information about the educational institution to the general public, to ensure the continuous communication of the employees and students with the educational institution. Also, several sites dedicated to education and upbringing can be combined in content and logic to form an educational portal.

Based on the above, it can be concluded that professors and teachers working in educational institutions, especially informatics teachers, and students who have great interest among the students of the educational institution, together create the site of this educational institution. are important participants in updating the content.

The teacher's control of students' knowledge based on computer technologies - The wide range of possibilities and simplicity of Internet technologies lead to an increase in the number of Internet users every minute. Among these users, students, students, and staff engaged in scientific research make up the majority. Based on this, it can be said that the use of Internet technologies in the educational process, in particular, the websites dedicated to educational institutions, helps to bring the quality and efficiency of education to a significantly higher level.

In the current conditions where new information technology tools are being improved and developed, the ability of young students studying in an educational institution (in general, those working in any field) to find the necessary information independently from the Internet system, is full of problems related to their current specialty that they face and is becoming one of the important conditions in being able to solve it correctly.

It is extremely important to first determine the types of Internet services and their nature when determining the possibilities of using Internet sites in the educational process and its effectiveness. It is these identified data that will help to distinguish organizational forms and methods of working on the Internet. Based on the classification, it is possible to get the working method of the internet. In this case, Internet server services should be divided into two types: information and communication services.

All sites created for an educational institution on the Internet can be divided into several types:

- educational Internet resources;
- consulting Internet resources;
- informative internet sources;
- evaluative Internet resources;
- Internet resources with presentations;

Each of them will be discussed below: Distance learning, virtual schools, labs and web classrooms are examples. Examples of Internet resources that provide advice include various teleconferences, virtual pedagogical councils, virtual methodical, associational problem councils, virtual cafes, etc.

Informational Internet sources include electronic textbooks, reference books, electronic libraries, dictionaries, catalogs, and virtual museums.

Evaluative Internet sources include testing, remote contests, various quizzes, and Olympiads.

It is possible to provide separate pages with detailed information about the educational directions of educational institutions to the presented Internet resources. With the help of sites created for educational institutions, teachers enable students to learn remotely. Sites created for educational institutions are especially convenient for learners who have difficulty attending the training places. In addition, students will acquire the culture, skills and competences of working with information technologies. The use of sites created for educational institutions in the course of the lesson creates great opportunities.

Teaching with the help of sites created for educational institutions includes the main forms of traditional organization of the educational process. These include lectures, seminars and practical exercises, laboratory practice, control system, scientific research and independent work of students. All these forms of organization of the educational process in practice allow the students to easily combine their independent knowledge activities with various information sources,

to quickly and systematically communicate with the teacher or tutor conducting the course, and for the students to work in groups.

The use of sites created for educational institutions during the educational process allows teachers to:

- Sharing experiences and methods with other colleagues using the Internet;
- individualization of the educational process by implementing different teaching methods for students of different categories at the same time;
- as a result of using control tasks on the sites created for educational institutions as exercises, bringing students' acquired knowledge of science to the level of skills and qualifications;
- creating an opportunity for students to work individually and demonstrate their abilities by reducing manual work;
- creates opportunities for students to effectively organize the process of independent learning.

The following advantages of sites created for educational institutions in the field of education can be listed: improvement of mastering of subjects; increasing network literacy (innovations in communicating with a computer and the Internet); improvement of attitude to learning; improvement of independent education and research skills; increase the efficiency of practical skills.

Thus, modern information technologies have a great opportunity for students in processes such as information delivery, storage, and search. Currently, many information and educational resources have been created in electronic form in educational institutions. A systematic approach to the creation and development of information-educational portals is necessary. Because in creating an educational environment based on portal technologies, it is important to have a good level of analytical preparation, to ensure the appropriateness of the content, and to ensure the systematization of information. The provided information and educational resources will include tasks for independent learning, tests to check acquired knowledge, tasks aimed at developing creative thinking, and exercises aimed at strengthening knowledge. Using the possibilities of new information technologies serves to eliminate difficulties in solving some pedagogical problems. An important condition for the development of a unified information-educational environment is the development of the educational and methodological support of the portal, the improvement of the creation of electronic educational publications.

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